

Empowering Education: AMCQA Generation with T5 Transformers

Radhwan Hussein Abdulzhraa AL-Sagheer*

*(Department of computer science, Faculty of education for girls, University of Kufa, Najaf, Iraq, radhwan.hu@uokufa.edu.iq)

Abstract:

The growing popularity of e-learning kits and the increasing number of online knowledge seekers in educational institutions such as universities, schools, childcare institutions and other scientific organizations have presented many challenges and difficulties for educators who are interested in creating modern tests.

This makes fair and effective assessment of students difficult, and a major obstacle is the manual formulation of test-style questions, which disrupts the smooth integration of educational activities and hinders the development of innovative teaching methods based on diverse questions. Therefore, there is an urgent need to explore modern solutions to help teachers overcome these difficulties and ensure a smooth testing process, accurate answers and fair assessment of students.

This paper introduces Empowerment Education (EE), a model specifically designed for automatic answering multiple choice questions (AMCQAs) from real-life texts. To overcome the challenges and obstacles that hinder the effective management of sequential tests, the model uses advanced natural language processing and machine learning tools based on the T5 architecture.

This system aims to simplify the generation of various contextually relevant questions to enhance students' knowledge and critical thinking abilities. In addition to being highly suitable for educational settings, it can have practical applications in an industrial context, facilitating knowledge-sharing and dissemination.

Keywords: Empowering Education, Automated Multiple-Choice Question Answering, Distractors, Question generation, Natural Language Processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multiple-choice question answering(MCQA) has gained popularity in education because it offers easy scoring and quick electronic processing, allowing for the evaluation of higher-order thinking[1,2].

However, one drawback is the time-consuming process of creating such questions, and the potential risk of encouraging guessing [3].

Nonetheless, the utilization of AMCQA for testing has proven effective in aiding the learning process and enhancing student memory retention [4].

To address these challenges, researchers have shifted their focus to automatic question generation [5].

Although these questions are applied in various fields and languages, manual creation of high-

quality stems remains a laborious and error-prone task [6].

Notably, during the COVID-19 outbreak, educators turned to AI-based e-learning tools, which significantly improved question generation and language-related tasks [7,8].

The research objective was to automate the generation of MCQA, simplify reading comprehension assessments, and promote greater student engagement. To address this problem, we developed a system that leverages natural language processing and machine-learning techniques using T5 transformers. The main goal was to simplify the process of creating diverse and contextually appropriate questions to test the students' knowledge and critical thinking skills.

EE follows a step-by-step process, starting with input-text analysis and data preparation. Significant keywords were extracted to create distractors for the subsequent questions.

The system generates questions using these distractors and creates additional distractors for correct options. The evaluation by human experts indicated that the questions and choices were phrased well.

II. RELATED WORK

Extensive research on automated question generation has explored diverse methods, including rule- and template-based approaches, along with recent advancements using data-driven techniques with neural networks and language models[9].

Education research focuses on using natural language processing (NLP) techniques to analyze educational content, assess student understanding, and provide personalized learning experiences[10].

Considerable investigations have been conducted on the employment of machine learning algorithms in educational assessment, with a specific emphasis

on MCQA. Scholars have devised models to automatically assess and assign scores to students' answers in a multiple-choice format[11].

Transformer-based language models such as BERT, GPT, and T5 have made remarkable progress in natural language understanding and generation tasks. These models have been effectively utilized in the field of education for tasks such as question generation, reading comprehension, and adaptive learning[12].

Prior research has concentrated on developing automated assessment systems that encompass question generation, the analysis of student responses, and personalized feedback. The goal of these systems is to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of educational assessments[13].

This study focuses on determining the efficiency of generating questions and comparing their quality with questions developed by people involved in student assessment. This study aims to provide an in-depth mechanism to demonstrate the effectiveness of using modern methods to create tests [14].

Previous studies have explored the relationship between students' integration with various scientific subjects using interactive questionnaires, indicating their impact on educational curriculum outcomes [15].

III. SYSTEM

T5 is a powerful language model that has contributed to the development of NLP tasks. T5 has the ability to generate MCQA, which plays a major role in developing educational settings, such as not wasting time for teachers in preparing tests, activating better evaluation processes based on accuracy and speed of achievement, announcing results to examiners, and taming educational experiences and skills.

The transformer architecture, particularly the T5 transformer, has gained a high reputation in the NLP field.

Unlike traditional attentional mechanisms featuring sequence-to-sequence architectures, transformers are encoding and decoding architectures based on attentional structures that provide training parallelism, resulting in larger models with reduced computational complexity, which lowers costs and speeds up the implementation. [16].

T5 has demonstrated impressive advancements in various NLP tasks and has valuable applications in generating MCQA for educational settings, benefiting educators by saving time, improving assessments, and enhancing personalized learning experiences.

The T5 architecture comprises of multiple layers of encoders and decoders. The encoders contain a single attention layer and a feed-forward network shared across all encoders. Decoders are similar to encoders, but include an additional layer of attention, known as "self-attention," which empowers the decoder to focus on relevant elements from the input. Different language models based on transformer architecture may utilize specific parts, such as GPT2, which uses only decoder blocks, and BERT relies solely on encoders[17].

Machine learning faces the challenge of fully retraining the models when new data are presented. Transformer Learning provides a solution by enabling knowledge learned in one domain to be reused in another, thereby relaxing the requirement for similar distributions in training and test datasets. Word embedding, such as GloVe and Word2Vec, is essential in NLP tasks and can be used in transfer learning to fine-tune models, such as BERT and T5, which have been pretrained on extensive corpora[18].

The T5 model employs the full Transformer architecture with a "Text-to-Text" interface and has

been pre-trained on multiple tasks, including question creation. This makes it highly suitable for educational applications, and the "Text-to-Text" interface simplifies the training and fine-tuning process, harnessing the advantages of transfer learning and language modelling [19].

The proposed pipeline for generating EE relies on the T5 models. The following subsections outline the process of generating AMCQA and provide detailed explanations for each step.

- A. Collecting textual information from diverse sources involves acquiring data in various formats, such as files (PDF, TXT and CSV), extracting content from websites through web scraping, and converting speech from videos into written text through transcription.
- B. Summarize the text to condense the accumulated data with a focus on important elements and remove unnecessary repetitions. Various summarization techniques are available; including the T5 transformer-based summarization method. This approach can create a brief and meaningful summary that effectively captures core information.
- C. Identify the significant keywords from the summarized text, diverting attention from the challenges of creating posts, various methods can be employed. Among these methods are TF-IDF, TextRank, TopicRank, YAKE, and KeyBERT. Each of these techniques offers distinct approaches to accomplishing this task. Each keyword serves as an answer(Correct Distractor) to the question created in the next step.
- D. Generating question-answering (QA) pairs, drawing on the results of the previous steps ,and pre-training T5 models with question generation QG and QA tasks, by fine-tuning the smaller version of the T5 Transformer with 220 million

parameters. The training used the SQuAD1.1 dataset, consisting of approximately one hundred thousand question-answer pairs. The goal was to generate questions and their answers, sometimes replacing the answer with the [MASKs] code with a 40 percent probability. The training process spanned six periods, with the best cross-entropy loss achieved in the fourth epoch reaching a value of 1.16. The optimization involved a learning rate of 0.0002, a batch size of 16, and a maximum symbol length of three hundred and eighty for the source and target.

E. Identifying the important incorrect distractors from the correct distractor (answer)for the QA pair obtained in the previous step can be achieved using different approaches. Some of these methods include WordNet, ConceptNet, and Sense2Vec. The objective is to ensure that the distractors are neither too similar nor too dissimilar to the correct answer but rather have a relevant association with the content.

To enhance our understanding of the preceding procedure, we employed the illustration shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Flowchart of AMCA Generation

Using the following example, we can elucidate the inputs and outputs of the system using data sourced from Wikipedia[20].

We furnished you with a text summary generated by the T5 converter, wherein the system-selected keywords are highlighted in bold.

Baghdad, the **capital of Iraq** and the **second-largest** city in the Arab world, lies along the Tigris River. It became the capital of the **Abbasid Caliphate** in 762 CE, rapidly growing into a prominent cultural, commercial, and intellectual hub of the Muslim world. Hosting prestigious institutions like the House of Wisdom, it earned the title "**Center of Learning**." During the Islamic Golden Age, Baghdad was the world's largest city with over a million inhabitants. However, it suffered **destruction** by the Mongol Empire in 1258, leading to a long period of decline marked by plagues and successive empires. In 1932, after Iraq gained independence, Baghdad regained some of its former glory as a significant center of **Arab culture** with a population of around 6 to 7 million. Despite its large population, the city occupies only 673 square kilometers. The Iraq War from 2003 to 2011 and subsequent **conflicts** caused severe infrastructural damage, affecting cultural heritage and historical artifacts. Baghdad experienced a high rate of **terrorist** attacks, but the frequency decreased after the defeat of the Islamic State militant group in Iraq in 2017. The origin of the name "Baghdad" is disputed, with various interpretations, but many associate it with **Middle Persian**, meaning "bestowed by God".

The system outputs from the previous summary are as follows:

What is the **capital of Iraq**?

- a) Cairo
- b) Damascus
- c) **Baghdad**
- d) Riyadh

What is the **second-largest city** in the Arab world?

- a) Cairo
- b) Damascus
- c) **Baghdad**
- d) Riyadh

When did Baghdad become the capital of the **Abbasid Caliphate**?

- a) 622 CE
- b) 750 CE
- c) **762 CE**
- d) 800 CE

Baghdad was known as the "**Center of Learning**" during which historical period?

- a) The Renaissance
- b) The Enlightenment
- c) The **Islamic Golden Age**
- d) The Industrial Revolution

What event caused the **destruction** of Baghdad by the Mongol Empire in 1258?

- a) The Black Death
- b) The Great Fire of Baghdad
- c) **Mongol Invasion**
- d) The Crusades

After gaining independence in 1932, Baghdad regained its former glory as a significant center of **Arab culture** with a population of approximately:

- a) 1 to 2 million
- b) 3 to 4 million
- c) **6 to 7 million**
- d) 9 to 10 million

Which **conflict** caused severe infrastructural damage and affected cultural heritage and historical artifacts in Baghdad?

- a) The Iran-Iraq War
- b) The Gulf War
- c) The **Iraq War (2003-2011)**
- d) The Syrian Civil War

When did the frequency of **terrorist** attacks in Baghdad decrease significantly?

- a) 2003
- b) 2011
- c) 2014
- d) **2017**

The origin of the name "Baghdad" is disputed, but many associate it with **Middle Persian**, meaning:

- a) "Desert Oasis"
- b) "City of Peace"
- c) "City of Wisdom"
- d) **"Bestowed by God"**

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

REFERENCES

- [1] Madri, Vijaya Raju, and Sreenivasulu Meruva. "A comprehensive review on MCQ generation from text." *Multimedia Tools and Applications* (2023): 1-20.
- [2] Coniam, David. "A preliminary inquiry into using corpus word frequency data in the automatic generation of English language cloze tests." *Calico Journal* (1997): 15-33.
- [3] Ch, Dhawaleswar Rao, and Sujana Kumar Saha. "Automatic multiple choice question generation from text: A survey." *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies* 13.1 (2018): 14-25.
- [4] Susanti, Yuni, et al. "Evaluation of automatically generated english vocabulary questions." *Research and practice in technology enhanced learning* 12 (2017): 1-21.
- [5] Rodriguez-Torrealba, Ricardo, Eva Garcia-Lopez, and Antonio Garcia-Cabot. "End-to-End generation of Multiple-Choice questions using Text-to-Text transfer Transformer models." *Expert Systems with Applications* 208 (2022): 118258.
- [6] Kumar, Archana Praveen, et al. "A Novel Framework for the Generation of Multiple Choice Question Stems Using Semantic and Machine-Learning Techniques." *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education* (2023): 1-44.
- [7] Liu, Qian, et al. "Multiple-choice questions (MCQs) for higher-order cognition: Perspectives of university teachers." *Innovations in Education and Teaching International* (2023): 1-13.
- [8] Agrawal, Arpit, and Pragya Shukla. "Context Aware Automatic Subjective and Objective Question Generation using Fast Text to Text Transfer Learning." *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications* 14.4 (2023).
- [9] Srivastava, Animesh, et al. "Questionator-automated question generation using deep learning." 2020 International Conference on

In this study, we introduced EE, which is a system designed for text AMCQA. The system demonstrates versatility by being applicable both in educational settings, such as classrooms, and in industrial environments; to identify knowledge gaps or serve as a self-assessment tool. Additionally, it can be seamlessly integrated with other systems to enhance the overall educational process, encompassing training scripts and documentation.

Looking ahead, our future work will involve exploring various larger pretrained transformers as the underlying model. Furthermore, we plan to augment the training data by incorporating additional data sources. Considering the scarcity of datasets tailored specifically for QG, we aimed to create a novel dataset by implementing EE in university courses. Subsequently, we collected and meticulously curated QA pairs generated over time using EE. These efforts will contribute to the continual enhancement and refinement of the system performance.

- Emerging Trends in Information Technology and Engineering (ic-ETITE). IEEE, 2020.
- [10] Chary, Michael, et al. "A review of natural language processing in medical education." *Western Journal of Emergency Medicine* 20.1 (2019): 78.
- [11] Korkmaz, Ceren, and Ana-Paula Correia. "A review of research on machine learning in educational technology." *Educational Media International* 56.3 (2019): 250-267.
- [12] Kalyan, Katikapalli Subramanyam, Ajit Rajasekharan, and Sivanesan Sangeetha. "Ammus: A survey of transformer-based pretrained models in natural language processing." *arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.05542* (2021).
- [13] Alemán, José Luis Fernández. "Automated assessment in a programming tools course." *IEEE transactions on education* 54.4 (2010): 576-581.
- [14] Nema, Preksha, and Mitesh M. Khapra. "Towards a better metric for evaluating question generation systems." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1808.10192* (2018).
- [15] Lin, Li-Chun, et al. "The impact of student engagement on learning outcomes in a cyber-flipped course." *Educational Technology Research and Development* 67 (2019): 1573-1591.
- [16] Vaswani, Ashish, et al. "Attention is all you need." *Advances in neural information processing systems* 30 (2017).
- [17] Raffel, Colin, et al. "Exploring the limits of transfer learning with a unified text-to-text transformer." *The Journal of Machine Learning Research* 21.1 (2020): 5485-5551.
- [18] Yigit, Gulsum, and Mehmet Fatih Amasyali. "Enhancing multiple-choice question answering through sequential fine-tuning and Curriculum Learning strategies." *Knowledge and Information Systems* (2023): 1-18.
- [19] Zhang, Wenxuan, et al. "M3Exam: A Multilingual, Multimodal, Multilevel Benchmark for Examining Large Language Models." *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.05179* (2023).
- [20] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Baghdad>